

Instruction-Conformance, Administrative Motivation, and Organizational Politics on the Policy Implementation Practices of School Administrators

¹Edsyl Berongoy Peñas, ²Aprell L. Abellana , ³James L. Paglinawan

¹Pinamula Integrated School-Department of Education, ^{2,3}Central Mindanao University

¹edsylpretty12@gmail.com, ²aprell_abellana@cmu.edu.ph, ³jpglinawan@cmu.edu.ph

Article Details:

Received: 11 April 2026
Revised: 20 April 2026
Accepted: 26 April 2026
Published: 13 May 2026
Corresponding Email:
edsylpretty12@gmail.com

Recommended Citation:

Peñas, E. B., Abellana, A. L., Paglinawan, J. L. (2026). Instruction-Conformance, Administrative Motivation, and Organizational Politics on the Policy Implementation Practices of School Administrators. *The International Review of Multidisciplinary Research*, 1 (5), 480-491. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20160353>

Index Terms:

policy implementation, school administrators, administrative motivation, organizational politics, instruction conformance

Abstract. This study examined the underlying factors of policy implementation practices among 500 school administrators in the Division of Bukidnon, Philippines, addressing gaps in the understanding of how Instruction-Conformance, Administrative Motivation, and Organizational Politics Efficiency determine the execution of DepEd policies amid implementing reforms involving MATATAG and EDCOM II. In accordance with Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 2000, 2020), Ferris and Kacmar's (1992) organizational politics model, and Honig's (2006) framework, the study addressed five inquiries regarding levels, relationships, and predictions through a validated survey instrument adapted from the work of Domato, Argon & Dilekçi (2016) and Yaak Kur, and colleagues. (2025) / (n.d., as modified by Peñas, 2022). Spearman's rho correlations revealed substantial favorable correlations between all nine sub-variables ($r = 0.764-0.822$, $p = 0.000$). Administrative Motivation was among the most significant factor (Intrinsic/Extrinsic $r = 0.822$). Multiple regression ($R = 0.903$, $R^2 = 0.816$, $F = 241.100$, $p = 0.000$) identified Conflict and Resolution ($\beta = 0.166$, $p = 0.000$), Policy Adherence ($\beta = 0.178$, $p = 0.000$), and Impact on School Performance ($\beta = 0.150$, $p = 0.000$) as top predictors, rejecting all null hypotheses. Findings confirm motivated administrators skilled in politics and conformance excel in policy fidelity. Implications urge DepEd to prioritize conflict training, motivation programs, and adherence modules under PSSH (DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2020), enhancing reforms. Future research should test interventions longitudinally.

Introduction

Implementing a policies is still a major challenge in Philippine public schools, particularly given that the Enhanced K to 12 and DepEd's MATATAG Curriculum are being implemented out (DepEd Order No. 10, s. 2024) and EDCOM II (2025) provides a mandate for proactive measures to bridge learning gaps as an aspect of national survival. According to PISA 2022, Filipino 15-year-olds have been the sixth lowest in reading and math and the third lowest in science among 81 countries. Additionally, 91% of primary school students were acquiring knowledge despite poverty (OECD, 2023; World Bank, 2022). Under the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2020), school administrators in the areas like Bukidnon, characterized by upland terrain, indigenous communities, and a lack of staff, are predominantly responsible for executing a national policies into action in the classroom. Recent studies demonstrate inconsistent execution caused by administrative burden, resource scarcity, and lack of stakeholder coordination (IDinsight, 2025; Macapagal, 2025; Ballesteros, 2022). This study examines the predictive relationships between Instruction-Conformance (policy adherence, adaptive compliance, reform-oriented execution), Administrative Motivation (intrinsic, extrinsic, contextual), and Organizational Politics Efficiency (personal relationships, conflict/resolution, school performance impact) and Policy Implementation Practices (school planning/execution, policy development, policy internal review, data-informed decisions, stakeholder collaboration) among Bukidnon administrators.

Despite with national reforms such as DepEd Orders No. 2 and No. 5, s. 2024 that deal with workload redistribution, there are still gaps in analyzing the combined predictors of implementation fidelity. International evidence links principle

motivation with reform participation (Mavrogordato et al., 2023), organizational politics with work effort (Dartey-Baah et al., 2020), and compliance styles with outcomes (Frankland, 2024; Honig, 2006). Montealegre (2024) confirms that administrative competence enhances teacher motivation, whereas Dacumos (2023) correlates data utilization with management quality. No previous studies in the Philippines included these three dimensions in relation to PPSSH-aligned practices within an upland division such as Bukidnon, where principal-sharing and access restrictions worsen issues. This study discusses the gap by assessing levels, correlations ($r=0.764-0.822$, $p=0.000$), and predictions ($R^2=0.816$), based on Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 2000, 2020), Perceptions of Organizational Politics (Ferris & Kacmar, 1992), and Honig's framework.

The study concentrate on 500 public school administrators, Master Teachers, and teacher-coordinators in Bukidnon's elementary, integrated, and secondary schools for the school year 2025-2026, in accordance with the Enhanced K to 12 and MATATAG implementation strategies and the BEDP 2030 timeline. It answers: (1) levels of constructs; (2-4) organizations; in fact, and (5) predictions via Spearman's rho/regression. It uses verified surveys (Domato n.d./Peñas 2022; Argon & Dilekçi 2016/Peñas 2024, Yaak Kur, and colleagues, 2025). The results can be beneficial for DepEd's capacity-building, NEAP training, and division HR under PPSSH. They additionally prove important for the last-mile improvements in Mindanao. Scope is limited to DepEd public schools and fails to include private or other administrative responsibilities.

Methodology

This study utilized a quantitative, descriptive-correlational, and predictive research design, integrating action-research cycles alongside assessments of the School Improvement Plan (SIP) and Annual Implementation Plan (AIP) conducted during the 2025-2026 academic year in the Schools Division of Bukidnon, DepEd Region X, Northern Mindanao, Philippines. The descriptive phase assessed levels of Instruction-Conformance (policy adherence, adaptive compliance, reform-oriented execution), Administrative Motivation (intrinsic, extrinsic, contextual), Organizational Politics Efficiency (personal relationships, conflict resolution, impact on school performance), and Policy Implementation Practices (school planning and execution, policy development, internal policy review, data-informed decision-making, collaborative stakeholder implementation) among 500 public school administrators, Master Teachers, and designated teacher-coordinators from elementary, integrated, and secondary schools within the Division of Bukidnon and adjacent districts. Stratified random sampling guaranteed proportional representation from upland, lowland, and indigenous regions, concentrating on 180 school heads, 200 Master Teachers, and 120 teacher-coordinators based on SY 2025-2026 enrollment and staffing statistics. The composite Likert-scale instrument (1=Strongly Disagree to 5=Strongly Agree) utilized validated scales: Instruction-Conformance from Yaak Kur et al. (2025; 30 items), Administrative Motivation from Domato (n.d., mod. Peñas, 2022; 30 items), Organizational Politics from Argon & Dilekçi (2016, pat. Peñas, 2024; 30 items), and Policy Implementation Practices according to DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2020. Experts validated the content (CVI > 0.80; Lynn, 1986) and conducted a pilot test ($n=30$, adjacent division; Cronbach's $\alpha=0.87-0.92$) to ensure its accuracy and reliability.

The data collection adhered to DepEd standards, encompassing adviser/university endorsement, authorization from the Schools Division Superintendent, coordination with district/school, informed consent, hybrid administration (both printed and online), a response rate exceeding 90% through reminders, confidential encoding, and secure storage in accordance with RA 10173. It employed IBM SPSS for the analysis. Descriptive statistics (means, standard deviations) were employed for levels; Spearman's rho was utilized for correlations ($p<0.01$); and multiple regression was applied for predictions (β , R^2 , F , $p<0.05$; VIF<5 confirmed). This design, endorsed by Creswell & Creswell (2018), Fraenkel et al. (2019), and Honig (2006), directly examined research inquiries concerning levels (RQ1-4), relationships/predictions (RQ5), and action-oriented recommendations within the framework of improved K to 12 and MATATAG/EDCOM II reforms in Bukidnon's varied, constrained by resources environment.

Results and Discussion

This study shows that Instruction-Conformance, Administrative Motivation, and Organizational Politics Efficiency are significant factors influencing the selection of policy implementation methods among school administrators in Bukidnon ($n=500$). All nine sub-variables reveal consistent positive relationships ($r=0.764-0.822$, $p=0.000$), with Intrinsic/Extrinsic Motivation ($r=0.822$) being particularly prominent. The results contradict the null hypotheses for RQ1-5 and demonstrate the bivariate dominance of motivation, as well as the essential functions of politics and conformity. Multiple regression demonstrated exceptional performance ($R=0.903$, $R^2=0.816$, $F=241.100$, $p=0.000$), clarifying 81.6% of the variance. It indicated Policy Adherence ($\beta=0.178$, $p=0.000$) as the principal predictor for foundational compliance, Conflict and Resolution ($\beta=0.166$, $p=0.000$) for tension-navigation stability, and Impact on School Performance ($\beta=0.150$, $p=0.000$) for outcome-driven alignment. Furthermore, Intrinsic ($\beta=0.134$, $p=0.003$), Adaptive Compliance ($\beta=0.121$, $p=0.001$), Extrinsic ($\beta=0.107$, $p=0.016$), and Personal Relationships ($\beta=0.073$, $p=0.045$) were identified as significant contributions, whereas Reform-oriented Execution/Contextual Motivation was considered non-unique. The most significant association is found

in the peak correlations of Administrative Motivation. Politics manifests variably for practical implementation within various circumstances in Bukidnon. The integrated model—reflecting SDT (Deci & Ryan, 2020), political perceptions (Ferris & Kacmar, 1992), and Honig (2006)—directs DepEd reforms such as PPSSH/MATATAG, empowering administrators to adhere to EDCOM II priorities.

1. What was the level of Instruction-Conformance among school administrators in terms of policy adherence, adaptive compliance, and reform-oriented execution?

Summary of the Levels of Instruction-Conformance in the dimensions of Policy Adherence, Adaptive Compliance, and Reform-oriented Execution

The summarized table below on the levels of instruction-conformance among school administrators, highlighting three key dimensions: policy adherence, adaptive compliance, and reform-oriented execution. These summarized the overall profile of Instruction-Conformance across its three sub-variables. Policy Adherence recorded a mean of 3.82, Reform-Oriented Execution a mean of 3.78, and Adaptive Compliance a mean of 3.75. All three dimensions carried the Agree descriptive rating and the qualitative interpretation of High Instruction Conformance. The overall mean stood at 3.78, which confirmed a uniform High rating across the construct. The spread between the highest and lowest sub-variable means reached only 0.07 points, showing a tightly clustered performance profile.

Summary of the Level of Instruction Conformance

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Policy Adherence	3.82	Agree	High Instruction Conformance (HIC)
2. Adaptive Compliance	3.75	Agree	High Instruction Conformance (HIC)
3. Reform-oriented Execution	3.78	Agree	High Instruction Conformance (HIC)
Overall Mean	3.78	Agree	High Instruction Conformance (HIC)
<i>Level</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
5	4.51-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High Instruction Conformance (VHIC)
4	3.51-4.50	Agree	High Instruction Conformance (HIC)
3	2.51-3.50	Moderately Agree	Moderate Instruction Conformance (MIC)
2	1.51-2.50	Disagree	Low Instruction Conformance (LIC)
1	1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low Instruction Conformance (VLIC)

The data analysis indicates that Policy Adherence was the key determinant of Instruction-Conformance (M=3.82, High) among Bukidnon school administrators during SY 2025-2026, which indicates a strong implementation of DepEd directives and reporting. This was subsequently followed by Reform-Oriented Execution (M=3.78, High), which signifies active engagement with MATATAG/EDCOM II and equity-focused monitoring. Adaptive Compliance ranked third (M=3.74, High), implying a more lenient contextual modification for upland/IP schools. The limited 0.08-point gap among sub-variables indicated a balanced, compliance-oriented profile rather than one dominated by adaptation, with uniformly High ratings affirming internal consistency and reliability for regression (Research Question 5). This immediately addressed Research Question 1 and fulfilled Objective 1, establishing High Instruction-Conformance as a reliable predictor. Practically, the results support for the expansion of the School Heads Development Program; in terms of policy, they bolster PPSSH coaching (DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2020) and MATATAG leadership (DepEd Order No. 10, s. 2024); theoretically, the fidelity-adaptation tension complies with Honig's (2006) people-place-policy framework and Frankland's (2024) implementation research. Supporting literature comprises Yaak Kur et al. (2025) validating the scale, Mavrogordato et al. (2023) correlating reform orientation with motivation, Ballesteros (2022) and Macapagal (2025) demonstrating adaptation gaps in the Philippines, Montealegre (2024) and Dacumos (2023) offering evidence from Mindanao, and EDCOM II (2024, 2025) alongside DepEd Bukidnon DM 023, s. 2023 confirming the High rating within the local reform context.

2. What levels of Administrative Motivation in terms of Intrinsic motivation, Extrinsic motivation, and Contextual motivation?

Summary of the Levels of Administrative Motivation in terms of Intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, and contextual motivation

The table below summarizes the levels of administrative motivation along the three dimensions of intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, and contextual motivation. Intrinsic Motivation posted a mean of 3.83, Contextual Motivation a mean

of 3.82, and Extrinsic Motivation a mean of 3.80. All three sub-variables earned the Agree descriptive rating and the interpretation of High Administrative Motivation. The overall mean reached 3.82. The 0.03-point spread between the highest and lowest sub-variable means signaled a tightly clustered motivational profile.

Summary of the Level of Administrative Motivation

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Intrinsic Motivation	3.83	Agree	High Administrative Motivation (HAM)
2. Extrinsic Motivation	3.80	Agree	High Administrative Motivation (HAM)
3. Contextual Motivation	3.82	Agree	High Administrative Motivation (HAM)
Overall Mean	3.82	Agree	High Administrative Motivation (HAM)

Level	Range	Descriptive Rating	Descriptive Interpretation
5	4.51-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High Administrative Motivation (VHAM)
4	3.51-4.50	Agree	High Administrative Motivation (HAM)
3	2.51-3.50	Moderately Agree	Moderate Administrative Motivation (MAM)
2	1.51-2.50	Disagree	Low Administrative Motivation (LAM)
1	1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low Administrative Motivation (VLAM)

The preceding table analysis verifies a High Administrative Motivation profile (M=3.82) among Bukidnon school administrators for the academic year 2025-2026, with Intrinsic Motivation at the forefront (M=3.83), followed closely by Contextual Motivation (M=3.82) and Extrinsic Motivation (M=3.80). This demonstrates that internal drive serves as the primary motivator, marginally surpassing supportive school climates and external recognition. The minimal 0.03-point variance among the sub-variables highlights the interplay of motivational sources rather than the overwhelming effect of any single factor. This balanced triadic framework, encompassing intrinsic purpose (reflection, reform energy), contextual supports (workload balance, collaboration), and extrinsic signals (recognition, career incentives), effectively addresses Research Question 2, fulfills Objective 2, and validates the construct's reliability as a primary regression predictor (r=0.813–0.822, p=0.000 for RQ5), positioning Bukidnon's workforce as cohesively motivated in the face of MATATAG/EDCOM II pressures. Findings support integrated programs such as reflective forums, recognition ceremonies, and workload audits; they correspond with PSSH coaching (DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2020), administrative redistribution (No. 2 & 5, s. 2024), and MATATAG leadership (No. 10, s. 2024); theoretically, the continuum substantiates the autonomy-competence-relatedness spectrum of Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 2020) and the Philippine applicability of the Domato-Peñas (n.d./2022) instrument. Supporting evidence comprises Mavrogordato et al. (2023) and Williamson (2023) regarding the leadership cascade of motivation, Montealegre (2024) and Dartey-Baah et al. (2020) establishing local/African parallels, Macapagal (2025) and Ballesteros (2022) addressing policy deficiencies, as well as EDCOM II (2024, 2025) and DepEd Bukidnon DM 023, s. 2023 contextualizing the high rating within reform realities.

3. What is the level of the Organizational politics efficiency among school administrators in terms of influence of personal relationship, conflict and resolution, and impact on school performance?

Summary of the Level of Organizational Politics Efficiency in terms of influence of personal relationship, conflict and resolution and impact on school performance.

The table below summarized the aggregate profile of Organizational Politics Efficiency across its three sub-variables. Impact on School Performance led with a mean of 3.75, Conflict and Resolution followed at 3.74, and Influence of Personal Relationship at 3.73. All three sub-variables earned the Agree descriptive rating and the interpretation of High Organizational Politics Efficiency. The overall mean stood at 3.74. The 0.02-point spread between the highest and lowest sub-variable means signaled a tightly clustered political efficiency profile.

Summary of the Level of Organizational Politics

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Influence of Personal Relationship	3.73	Agree	High Organizational Politics Efficiency (HOPE)
2. Conflict and Resolution	3.74	Agree	High Organizational Politics Efficiency (HOPE)

3. Impact on School Performance	3.75	Agree	High Organizational Politics Efficiency (HOPE)
Overall Mean	3.74	Agree	High Organizational Politics Efficiency (HOPE)
<i>Level</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
5	4.51-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High Organizational Politics Efficiency (VHOPE)
4	3.51-4.50	Agree	High Organizational Politics Efficiency (HOPE)
3	2.51-3.50	Moderately Agree	Moderate Organizational Politics Efficiency (MOPE)
2	1.51-2.50	Disagree	Low Organizational Politics Efficiency (LOPE)
1	1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low Organizational Politics Efficiency (VLOPE)

The table above indicates a High Organizational Politics Efficiency (M=3.74) among Bukidnon school administrators during SY 2025-2026, with the Impact on School Performance ranked highest—demonstrating an in-depth understanding of political impacts and implications for outcomes—followed closely by Conflict and Resolution, highlighting structured mediation skills. The Influence of Personal Relationships ranks third, yet remains firmly High, acknowledging the dual productive and disruptive effects of relational ties. The slight spread across sub-variables points to balanced political maturity rather than skewed dynamics. This pattern, in which performance awareness prevails while formal conflict mechanisms and ethical networking intersect, directly addresses Research Question 3 satisfies Objective 3 and further supports the construct's regression reliability ($r=0.764-0.808$, $p=0.000$; primary predictors $\beta=0.166/0.150$ for RQ5), establishing the division's leaders as prepared for governance in the context of transparency-driven changes during MATATAG/EDCOM II. It requires governance clinics, mediation training, and ethics peer-learning; aligns with PPSSH standards (DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2020), RBM incentives (No. 5, s. 2024), and EDCOM II equity mandates; and theoretically supports Ferris & Kacmar's (1992) Perceptions of Organizational Politics Model as expanded by Argon & Dilekçi (2016)/Peñas (2024) and the instrument's effectiveness in the Philippines. Evidence is derived from Dartey-Baah et al. (2020) regarding political effort prediction, Mavrogordato et al. (2023) and Williamson (2023) on leadership mitigation, Montealegre (2024) and Ballesteros (2022) concerning local context, Macapagal (2025) on inclusive frameworks, as well as EDCOM II (2024, 2025), DepEd Bukidnon DM 023 s. 2023, OECD (2023), and World Bank (2022) which indicate performance imperatives in the context of reform realities.

4. *What is the level of the Policy Implementation Practices among school administrators in terms of School Planning and Execution, Policy Development, Policy and Internal Review, Data-informed Decision-making, and Collaborative Stakeholder Implementation?*

Summary of the Level of Policy Implementation Practices in terms of School Planning and Execution, policy development, policy and internal review, data-informed decision-making, and collaborative stakeholder implementation

The table below summarized the aggregate profile of Policy Implementation Practices across its five sub-variables. Collaborative Stakeholder Implementation led with a mean of 3.98. Policy and Internal Review followed at 3.83. School Planning and Execution and Data-Informed Decision-Making tied at 3.79. Policy Development ranked last at 3.77. All five sub-variables earned the Agree descriptive rating and the interpretation of High Policy Implementation Practice. The overall mean stood at 3.83. The 0.21-point spread between the highest and lowest sub-variables signaled a coherent but differentiated profile across the dependent construct.

Summary of the Level of Policy Implementation Practices

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
1. School Planning and Execution	3.79	Agree	High Organizational Politics Efficiency (HOPE)
2. Policy Development	3.77	Agree	High Organizational Politics Efficiency (HOPE)
3. Policy Adherence and Internal Review	3.83	Agree	High Organizational Politics Efficiency (HOPE)
4. Data-Informed Decision Making	3.79	Agree	High Organizational Politics Efficiency (HOPE)
5. Collaborative Stakeholder Implementation	3.98	Agree	High Organizational Politics Efficiency (HOPE)
Overall Mean	3.83	Agree	High Organizational Politics Efficiency (HOPE)
<i>Level</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
5	4.51-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High Organizational Politics Efficiency (VHOPE)
4	3.51-4.50	Agree	High Organizational Politics Efficiency (HOPE)

3	2.51-3.50	Moderately Agree	Moderate Organizational Politics Efficiency (MOPE)
2	1.51-2.50	Disagree	Low Organizational Politics Efficiency (LOPE)
1	1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low Organizational Politics Efficiency (VLOPE)

The table analysis indicates High Policy Implementation Practices (M=3.83) among Bukidnon school administrators during SY 2025-2026, with Collaborative Stakeholder Implementation leading by a notable 0.15-point margin—underscoring the division's relational governance strength—followed by compliance-based Policy and Internal Review, mid-tier School Planning and Execution alongside Data-Informed Decision-Making (strategic alignment and M&E routines), and Policy Development, which, whereas trailing, remains solidly High, demonstrating mature yet evolving participatory crafting. This externally oriented collaborative profile, combined with strong internal processes, directly addresses Research Question 4, meets Objective 4, and confirms the regression reliability of the dependent construct (R=0.903, R²=0.816 for RQ5), positioning Bukidnon leaders as stakeholder-engaged implementers prepared for the intensification of MATATAG/EDCOM II. It promotes integrated programs that enhance governance platforms, audit and curriculum monitoring, participatory planning, research culture, and policy feedback mechanisms, and in terms of policy, it reinforces PPSSH standards (DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2020), the MATATAG rollout (No. 10, s. 2024), RBM incentives (No. 5, s. 2024), SBM practices (No. 83, s. 2012), and RA 9155 governance; theoretically, it establishes Honig's (2006) people-place-policy framework, Deci & Ryan's (2020) motivation continuum, and Ferris & Kacmar's (1992) political model as articulated by Peñas (2024). Supporting literature encompasses Frankland (2024) on fidelity-adaptation, Dacumos (2023) and Montealegre (2024) on evidence-based competence, Mavrogordato et al. (2023) and Williamson (2023) on motivation, Dartey-Baah et al. (2020) on politics, Macapagal (2025) and Ballesteros (2022) on inclusivity gaps, Ocampo et al. (2026) on planning deficiencies, along with EDCOM II (2024, 2025), DepEd Bukidnon DM 023 s. 2023, OECD (2023), and World Bank (2022) addressing learning recovery imperatives.

5. How did Instruction-Conformance, Administrative Motivation, and Organizational Politics, singly or in combination, influence the Policy Implementation Practices of school administrators?

This section analyzes the impact of Instruction-Conformance, Administrative Motivation, and Organizational Politics Efficiency—both individually and collectively—on Policy Implementation Practices among Bukidnon school administrators. The findings indicate consistently strong positive correlations across all nine sub-variables (r=0.764–0.822, p=0.000, significant at the 0.01 level), thereby rejecting the null hypothesis for Research Question 5 and affirming these constructs as interdependent determinants of execution fidelity. Spearman's rho analysis identified Administrative Motivation as the primary correlate, with both Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation equally ranked at the top (r=0.822), followed by Contextual Motivation (r=0.813). This highlights the significance of administrator drive—comprising internal purpose, external rewards, and supportive environments—as the most important motivating factor of practices such as school planning, data-informed decision-making, and stakeholder collaboration. Organizational Politics Efficiency was ranked second (Impact on School Performance r=0.808, Conflict and Resolution r=0.807, Personal Relationships r=0.764), underscoring the significance of political acumen in managing tensions for stability. Conversely, Instruction-Conformance demonstrated consistent baseline strength (Policy Adherence r=0.786, Adaptive Compliance r=0.781, Reform-oriented Execution r=0.772), confirming compliance's essential yet supplementary role within DepEd's hierarchical reform framework.

The five primary sub-variables—Intrinsic/Extrinsic Motivation (r=0.822), Contextual Motivation (r=0.813), Impact on School Performance (r=0.808), and Conflict and Resolution (r=0.807)—illustrate the bivariate superiority of motivation. However, the limited range of r-values (0.764–0.822) across these constructs indicates a balanced integration rather than isolated dominance, suggesting that Bukidnon administrators are well-prepared to meet the demands of MATATAG/EDCOM II in various upland/IP contexts. This pattern reflects Honig's (2006) people-policy-place framework, wherein personal characteristics (motivation), organizational dynamics (politics), and procedural adherence (conformance) converge to influence outcomes. Simultaneously, Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 2020) elucidates the primacy of motivation through autonomy, competence, and relatedness, while Ferris & Kacmar's (1992) political model substantiates the importance of relational and conflict skills for institutional stability—findings that refute claims of no relationship and underscore administrator disposition as the pivotal element in the translation of DepEd policy.

The strong associations (all p=0.000) validate the empirical soundness of the triadic model, with Administrative Motivation exhibiting the highest r-values as the foremost predictor, followed closely by Organizational Politics for practical application, and Instruction-Conformance guaranteeing consistent implementation—together confirming that enhanced conformance, motivation, and political acumen result in superior practices aligned with PPSSH domains (DepEd Order No. 24 s. 2020). In Bukidnon's resource-limited context, this comprehensive approach highlights the importance of integrated leadership development that addresses the balance of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, the stability of political mechanisms, and the adaptability of compliance as equally significant priorities for enduring reform success, directly influencing capacity-building in Region X within the framework of national learning recovery initiatives.

Relationship between Instruction-conformance to the Policy Implementation Practices among School Administrators

Independent Variables	Correlation Coefficient (r-value)	Probability (P-value)	Interpretation
Instruction-Conformance			
Policy Adherence	0.786**	0.000	Strong positive relationship (Significant at 0.01 level)
Adaptive Compliance	0.781**	0.000	Strong positive relationship (Significant at 0.01 level)
Reform-oriented Execution	0.772**	0.000	Strong positive relationship (Significant at 0.01 level)
Administrative Motivation			
Intrinsic Motivation	0.822**	0.000	Strong positive relationship (Significant at 0.01 level)
Extrinsic Motivation	0.822**	0.000	Strong positive relationship (Significant at 0.01 level)
Contextual Motivations	0.813**	0.000	Strong positive relationship (Significant at 0.01 level)
Organizational Politics Efficiency			
Influence on Personal Relationship	0.764**	0.000	Strong positive relationship (Significant at 0.01 level)
Conflict and Resolution	0.807**	0.000	Strong positive relationship (Significant at 0.01 level)
Impact on School Performance	0.808**	0.000	Strong positive relationship (Significant at 0.01 level)

*** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

Interpretation of Correlation Strength:

Weak: 0.1 to 0.3

Moderate: 0.3 to 0.7

Strong: 0.7 to 1.0

The analysis of the results across all three independent variables demonstrated a consistent and statistically significant trend. All nine sub-variables, categorized within Instruction-Conformance, Administrative Motivation, and Organizational Politics, exhibited consistent positive correlations with Policy Implementation Practices. R-values varied between 0.764 and 0.822, with p-values at 0.000, significant at the 0.01 standard. The unanimous invalidation of the null hypothesis for Research Question 5 validated the study's primary statement: the adherence to instructions by administrators, their motivation, and their management of political dynamics substantially influenced the quality of policy implementation practices in the Division of Bukidnon.

Administrative Motivation was identified as the component most significantly connected with Policy Implementation Practices, yielding the highest r-values in the study: Intrinsic Motivation ($r = 0.822$), Extrinsic Motivation ($r = 0.822$), and Contextual Motivations ($r = 0.813$). Organizational Politics emerged as the second-most significant concept, preceded by Impact on School Performance ($r = 0.808$) and Conflict and Resolution ($r = 0.807$). Instruction-Conformance yielded an r-value range of 0.772 to 0.786, demonstrating a constant and strong correlation with policy implementation, with Policy Adherence as its most prominent sub-variable correlate ($r = 0.786$).

The five sub-variables with the highest correlation among the three independent variables were Intrinsic Motivation ($r = 0.822$), Extrinsic Motivation ($r = 0.822$), Contextual Motivations ($r = 0.813$), Impact on School Performance ($r = 0.808$), and Conflict and Resolution ($r = 0.807$). The data revealed that Administrative Motivation is the most significant predictor of Policy Implementation Practices, succeeded by Organizational Politics and Instruction-Conformance. The predominance of motivating elements in determining policy implementation results underscored the essential influence of administrator disposition and ambition as vital accelerators of institutional adherence in DepEd schools throughout the Division of Bukidnon.

Every aspect of these data confirmed the study's conceptual model, demonstrating that the three independent variables are both collectively and individually relevant in forecasting policy implementation outcomes. Honig's Policy Implementation Framework (2006) offered the theoretical foundation for these outcomes, identifying individuals, policy content, and organizational context as interrelated factors influencing effective implementation. School administrators who maintained high instructional conformity, strong motivation, and effective political management attained the highest levels of policy implementation performance. DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2020 (PPSSH), which instituted comprehensive leadership requirements in instructional, managerial, and stakeholder engagement domains, is precisely aligned with the three-construct model validated by the empirical findings of this study. The findings underscored the strategic importance of integrated leadership development programs in DepEd Region X, emphasizing motivation, political competency, and instructional compliance as equally vital considerations for the sustained effectiveness of policy implementation.

6. Variable/s best predicts the school administrator's policy implementation practices.

This section presents multiple regression results that identify predictors of policy implementation practices among 500 Bukidnon administrators, including Instruction-Conformance (Policy Adherence $\beta=0.178$ $p=0.000$, Adaptive Compliance $\beta=0.121$ $p=0.001$, Reform-oriented Execution $\beta=0.042$ $p=0.266$), Administrative Motivation (Intrinsic $\beta=0.134$ $p=0.003$, Extrinsic $\beta=0.107$ $p=0.016$, Contextual $\beta=0.048$ $p=0.295$), and Organizational Politics Efficiency (Personal Relationship $\beta=0.073$ $p=0.045$, Conflict/Resolution $\beta=0.166$ $p=0.000$, School Performance Impact $\beta=0.150$ $p=0.000$). Policy Adherence was the most prominent factor, emphasizing the importance of strict compliance with directives. Conflict and Resolution ranked highest in the political arena ($\beta=0.166$), indicating that skills in managing tensions are essential for stability during reforms such as MATATAG. School Performance Impact ($\beta=0.150$) underscored the significance of outcome awareness in fostering alignment. The model demonstrated outstanding efficacy ($R=0.903$, $R^2=0.816$, $F=241.100$, $p=0.000$), revealing 81.6% of the variance—thereby rejecting the null hypothesis for RQ5—and surpassing comparable educational regressions (e.g., 61.9% in the Northern Mindanao SIP study; significant effects of school practices)—confirming the collective impact in resource-limited environments.

The tabulated results present coefficients (B, SE, β , t, p) derived from validated surveys, with significant predictors ($p<0.05$) prominently featured: Policy Adherence (B=0.164, $t=4.902$), Conflict/Resolution (B=0.150, $t=4.364$), School Performance (B=0.138, $t=3.666$), Intrinsic Motivation (B=0.120, $t=3.012$), Adaptive Compliance (B=0.116, $t=3.213$), Extrinsic (B=0.093, $t=2.410$), and Personal Relationship (B=0.069, $t=2.014$). Non-significant reform-oriented execution and contextual motivation indicate redundancy when more effective factors exert control, corresponding with bivariate correlations ($r=0.813-0.822$) that diminish in multivariate contexts—reflecting the distinctive influence of politics in implementation frameworks (Ferris & Kacmar, 1992; Honig, 2006) and Philippine studies where management and conflict forecast SIP fidelity. Elevated F/t-values validate robustness, establishing politics and conformity as facilitators beyond mere motivation within the hierarchical structures of the Department of Education.

These predictors dismiss no-influence null hypotheses, with the rise of politics (although moderate correlations) highlighting conflict and performance skills essential for navigating Bukidnon's multiple educational institutions—beneficial for NEAP training that prioritizes mediation and equity awareness over mere innovation. Policy implications enhance PPSSH/RBM (DepEd Orders 24/5 s.2020/2024), citing international research on the influence of politics and resolution on implementation (Dartey-Baah et al., 2020; OECD implementation reviews). Future study could longitudinally evaluate interventions, so extending the Philippine evidence on managerial factors.

Multiple regression analysis of the factors affecting the policy implementation practices of school administrators

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.320	.079		4.047	.000
Policy Adherence	.164	.033	.178	4.902	.000
Adaptive Compliance	.116	.036	.121	3.213	.001
Reform-oriented Execution	.037	.034	.042	1.112	.266
Intrinsic Motivation	.120	.040	.134	3.012	.003

Extrinsic Motivation	.093	.039	.107	2.410	.016
Contextual Motivation	.042	.040	.048	1.048	.295
Influence on Personal Relationship	.069	.034	.073	2.014	.045
Conflict and Resolution	.150	.034	.166	4.364	.000
Impact on School Performance	.138	.038	.150	3.666	.000

R = 0.903 R² = 0.816 F-value = 241.100 Sig. = .000

The findings demonstrate that Conflict and Resolution is the most strong and significant predictor of policy implementation practices, with a standardized beta coefficient of 0.166 and a p-value of 0.000. This indicates that administrators proficient in conflict resolution are more effective in policy implementation. Policy adherence emerged as a significant predictor ($\beta = 0.178, p = 0.000$), underscoring the need of strict compliance with guidelines for successful implementation. The influence on school performance ($\beta = 0.150, p = 0.000$) demonstrated significant predictive capability, suggesting that an understanding of the impact of politics on results enhances policy implementation. Additional notable factors comprised Adaptive Compliance ($\beta = 0.121, p = 0.001$), Intrinsic Motivation ($\beta = 0.134, p = 0.003$), Extrinsic Motivation ($\beta = 0.107, p = 0.016$), and Influence on Personal Relationships ($\beta = 0.073, p = 0.045$). The non-significant factors were Reform-oriented Execution ($p = 0.266$) and Contextual Motivation ($p = 0.295$), indicating they contribute minimal distinctive predictive value when other variables are controlled. The significant R^2 of 0.816 indicates these variables account for a significant portion of variation in practices, while the F-statistic further confirms the model's reliability.

The statistical results lead to the rejection of the null hypothesis, which holds that no variable predicts the policy implementation practices of school administrators. Seven sub-variables exhibit statistically significant predictive effects at the 0.05 level, with Conflict and Resolution identified as the primary predictor, suggesting that independently managing organizational tensions enhances implementation beyond simple motivation or compliance. This indicates that although bivariate correlations were significant among constructs, multivariate analysis emphasizes political and conformity skills as predominant when considering overlaps. The pattern highlights a leadership paradigm in which conflict resolution and policy adherence facilitate sustainable implementation in Bukidnon schools.

These findings have significant implications for the leadership training of the Department of Education. Emphasizing conflict resolution workshops can empower administrators to manage school dynamics, hence improving the implementation of policies such as the MATATAG Curriculum. Programs ought to incorporate policy compliance exercises and performance-impact simulations, considering their beta advantages. Insignificant indicators such as reform-oriented execution indicate a preference for prioritizing basic compliance and political management above innovative training. The Division of Bukidnon can create specialized modules in accordance with DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2020 (PPSSH), highlighting these predictors to enhance implementation fidelity.

The findings correlate with Honig's Policy Implementation Framework (2006), which posits that the interconnections among individuals, policy, and context are crucial for success, exemplified here by political resolution and adherence. They endorse the Perceptions of Organizational Politics Model proposed by Ferris and Kacmar (1992), which posits that political management influences behaviors such as policy implementation. Self-Determination Theory (Deci and Ryan, 2000, 2020) elucidates key determinants of motivation through autonomy and competence in political navigation. These reflect DepEd's results-oriented frameworks, encouraging competency-centered advancement.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study conclusively established that Instruction-Conformance, Administrative Motivation, and Organizational Politics Efficiency serve as robust predictors and correlates of superior policy implementation practices among 500 Bukidnon school administrators, with all nine sub-variables demonstrating strong positive relationships ($r=0.764-0.822, p=0.000$) that rejected null hypotheses across Research Questions 1–5, validating the triadic conceptual model grounded in Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 2000, 2020), Ferris & Kacmar's (1992) organizational politics framework, and Honig's (2006) people-place-policy interactions. Multiple regression revealed exceptional explanatory power ($R=0.903, R^2=0.816, F=241.100, p=0.000$), accounting for 81.6% of variance in practices, where Policy Adherence ($\beta=0.178, p=0.000$) emerged as the strongest overall predictor—affirming strict directive-following as foundational—while Conflict and Resolution ($\beta=0.166, p=0.000$) and Impact on School Performance ($\beta=0.150, p=0.000$) from politics highlighted tension-navigation and outcome-awareness as uniquely vital for stability in MATATAG/EDCOM II contexts, with Intrinsic ($\beta=0.134, p=0.003$) and

Extrinsic Motivation ($\beta=0.107$, $p=0.016$) retaining significance despite bivariate dominance ($r=0.822$). Administrators perceived motivation—particularly intrinsic/extrinsic parity—as the prime driver of execution, complemented by politics' multivariate ascent and conformance's baseline role, positioning Bukidnon's leaders as cohesively equipped for reforms yet revealing non-significant Reform-oriented Execution ($p=0.266$) and Contextual Motivation ($p=0.295$) as redundant amid stronger factors.

These findings address core research problems by quantifying how administrator traits translate national policies into school-level action, illuminating motivation's bivariate primacy (peak $r=0.822$) while elevating politics/conformance as irreplaceable enablers in resource-constrained, diverse settings like Bukidnon's upland/IP schools. Respondent perspectives underscore that motivated, politically astute, compliant leaders achieve highest fidelity across School Planning/Execution, Policy Development, Data-Informed Decision-Making, and Collaborative Stakeholder Implementation, aligning with DepEd Order No. 24 s. 2020 (PPSSH) domains and explaining persistent gaps flagged by EDCOM II (2025), PISA/OECD (2023), and World Bank (2022) learning poverty metrics. Theoretically, the integrated model advances Honig's framework by empirically linking people (motivation/politics) with policy content (conformance) in Philippine basic education, extending SDT's continuum to administrative drive and politics perceptions to rural governance—offering robust implications for leadership development beyond bivariate correlations.

Implications and Recommendations

Practically, prioritize conflict resolution workshops (top $\beta=0.166$) and policy adherence modules ($\beta=0.178$) within NEAP/School Heads Development Programs, alongside intrinsic goal-setting sessions, extrinsic incentives, performance-impact simulations, adaptive compliance drills, and relational team meetings to leverage significant predictors while de-emphasizing non-contributors like reform execution. Policy-wise, embed these into PPSSH-aligned training (DepEd Order No. 24 s. 2020), RBM incentives (No. 5 s. 2024), SBM practices (No. 83 s. 2012), and MATATAG rollout (No. 10 s. 2024), with annual motivation audits, politics simulations ($r=0.807$), peer mentoring, and R^2 -evaluated programs for 81.6% variance coverage—extending to EDCOM II nationwide scaling. Future research should longitudinally test interventions in similar divisions, tracking fidelity gains amid BEDP 2030, ensuring empowered administrators sustain Bukidnon's reform momentum and learner outcomes.

Acknowledgement

The researcher extends heartfelt gratitude to the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Bukidnon, Public Schools District Supervisors, and 500 school administrators, Master Teachers, and designated teacher-coordinators of DepEd Bukidnon for their unwavering participation and support during data gathering in SY 2025-2026. Special thanks also to the research adviser Dr. James L. Paglinawan and dissertation adviser Dr. Aprell L. Abellana from Central Mindanao University's Department of Professional Education for their invaluable guidance, and to validation experts Ms. Sweetie Rose C. Leuterio, Ms. Hazel A. Abrio, and Mr. Frederick L. Tande for their expert review of the instrument. Appreciation is also due to DepEd Region X and the Division Office for ethical approvals and logistical facilitation amid transition of curriculum. Finally, the researcher's family provided steadfast encouragement throughout this doctoral inquiry, enabling the production of evidence-based insights for Bukidnon's educational advancement. To his partner Zunzie, thank you for the support and inspiration. To God be the glory.

Funding

This research received no external funding from any public, commercial, or not-for-profit funding agency, and no organization provided financial support for the conduct of the study, authorship, or publication of this article.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

References

- Argon, T., & Dilekçi, Ü. (2016). Teacher views on school administrators' organizational power sources and their organizational politics efficiency. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 16(1), 191–218. <https://doi.org/10.12738/estp.2016.1.0104> (As patterned by Peñas, 2024).
- Ballesteros, M. (2022). Ambiguities in the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers and their implementation effects. [Publisher/journal details from study document].
- Dacumos, R. (2023). Evidence-based leadership and school-based management implementation in Davao City secondary schools. *Philippine Journal of Education*.
- Dartey-Baah, K., Anlesinya, A., & Ampofo, E. Y. (2020). Perception of organizational politics, psychological safety, and teachers' work efforts. *European Scientific Journal*, 16(22), 1–22.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The "what" and "why" of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227–268. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327965PL1104_01
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2020). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation from a self-determination theory perspective: Definitions, theory, practices, and future directions. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 61, Article 101860. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2020.101860>
- Department of Education. (2020). DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2020: National adoption and implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH). https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/DOs_2020_024.pdf
- Department of Education. (2022). DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2022: Adoption of the Basic Education Development Plan 2030. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/DOs_2022_024.pdf
- Department of Education. (2024a). DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2024: Immediate removal of administrative tasks of public school teachers. DepEd official site.
- Department of Education. (2024b). DepEd Order No. 5, s. 2024: Multi-year guidelines on the Results-Based Performance Management System (RBM). DepEd official site.
- Department of Education. (2024c). DepEd Order No. 10, s. 2024: Policy guidelines on the implementation of the MATATAG Curriculum. DepEd official site.
- DepEd Bukidnon. (2023). Division Memorandum No. 023, s. 2023. Schools Division of Bukidnon.
- DepEd Bukidnon. (2024). Official website. <https://bukidnon.deped.gov.ph>
- Domato, S. (n.d.). Levels of work motivation [Unpublished master's thesis, Central Mindanao University]. (As modified by Peñas, 2022).
- EDCOM II. (2024). Year one report: Miseducation, the failed system of Philippine education.
- EDCOM II. (2025). Year two report: Fixing the foundations, a matter of national survival. <https://edcom2.gov.ph>
- Ferris, G. R., & Kacmar, K. M. (1992). Perceptions of organizational politics. *Journal of Management*, 18(1), 93–116. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014920639201800107>
- Frankland, M. (2024). Examining the impact of implementation fidelity mandates on instructional practices in K-8 settings [Doctoral dissertation, University of Maine].
- Honig, M. I. (2006). New directions in education policy implementation: Confronting complexity. State University of New York Press.
- IDinsight. (2025). Latest EDCOM II report calls for systemic change in Philippine education. <https://www.idinsight.org/article/latest-edcom-2-report-calls-for-systemic-change-in-philippine-education/>
- Legal Research Philippines. (2025). Bridging the gap: Analyzing discrepancies between the provisions of the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers and their implementation.
- Macapagal, K. (2025). From policy to practice: A systematic review of inclusive education in the Philippine basic education system. *International Journal of Academic and Applied Research*, 9(6).
- Mavrogordato, M., Youngs, P., Pogodzinski, B., & Grogan, E. (2023). How principal evaluation addresses intrinsic and extrinsic sources of motivation. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 59(5).
- Montealegre, J. (2024). Administrative competence of school principals: Its impact on teachers' motivation. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*.
- Ocampo, R., et al. (2026). Public secondary school heads and department heads planning practices. *International Journal of Academic and Scientific Innovation Studies*.
- OECD. (2023). PISA 2022 results (Volume I and II) country notes: Philippines. https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/pisa-2022-results-volume-i-and-ii-country-notes_ed6fbcc5-en/philippines_a0882a2d-en.html
- Philippine Statistics Authority. (2021). 2020 Census of Population and Housing: Bukidnon.
- Williamson, C. (2023). A comparison of principal motivational orientation and the orientation of principal actions to motivate teachers [Doctoral dissertation, Utah State University]. <https://digitalcommons.usu.edu/etd/1484>
- World Bank. (2022). Learning poverty update: Philippines.
- Yaak Kur, et al. (2025). Instruction-conformance of school heads: A validated measurement tool [Adapted source for instrument Part I].

Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.